

ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY OF *ACMELLA ULIGINOSA* (SW.) CASS. FLOWER METHANOLIC EXTRACT ON MEMBRANE STABILIZATION AND PROTEIN DENATURATION: AN *IN-VITRO* EVALUATION

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ABSTRACT

The floral part of *Acmella uliginosa* plant is a common folklore pain-killer used in India and tropical countries. The plant possesses potent anti-arthritis property as well. To establish the anti-inflammatory activity of the methanolic flower extract *in vitro*, the human RBC membrane stabilizing activity and protein denaturation inhibiting activity were assessed. The results showed that the red blood cell suspension treated with flower extract displayed very significant membrane stabilization compared to untreated group. Plant extract, when incubated with RBC suspension at a dose of 400 µg/ml showed 39.37±3.63 % stabilization in hypotonicity induced RBC membrane haemolysis and 25.22±0.98% stabilization in heat induced RBC membrane haemolysis when compared to untreated groups. Similar result was found in protein denaturation inhibition test. The extract treated hen's egg albumin showed significantly less denaturation (26.52±2.39%) compared to untreated group. The present study firmly indicated the role of *Acmella uliginosa* flower extract as a potent anti-inflammatory agent.

Key Words: *Acmella uliginosa*, inflammation, membrane stabilization, protein denaturation, complementary and alternative medicine, haemolysis.

INTRODUCTION

Inflammation is a common complex biological process in response to tissue injury, infection, toxin exposure or chemical irritation. At the site of injury and tissue damage, inflammation is initiated by aggregation of immune cells from blood vessels and release of immune reaction mediators to eliminate foreign pathogens, resolving infection and repairing injured tissues. The main function of inflammation is protective which is rapid and self-limiting, but when prolonged, it may cause various chronic disorders and enhance extensive tissue damage. To treat the consequences inflammation, anti-inflammatory agents like non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) or steroids are available commercially. However, the consumption of these conventional NSAIDs leads to different side effects such as vomiting, dizziness, bleeding and

ulcers in the stomach and intestine [FDA Guideline (www.fda.gov)], liver damage (Bessone, 2010), renal impairment, chronic kidney disease (Nderitu *et al.*, 2013) and an increased risk of cardiovascular diseases (Trelle *et al.*, 2011).

Herbs play a major role in modern medicines. The herbal resources constitute a major reservoir for potentially active medicinal compounds all over the World. The development and use of herbal medicinal systems known as complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) has come into consideration due to their low side effects, low costing, and ready availability. Countries rich in biodiversity, including India, show herbal medicine practices from ancient era. Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani have been a major remedy against different odd diseases. In CAM system, daily consumption of raw

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and unprocessed plant parts or their formulations are said to have disease ameliorating properties (WHO, 1998). However, the potentiality and dose specificity of such crude plant upon consumption or application has been questioned in the modern medicinal system and in the light of experimental biology, these questions are being answered. In the last few decades, many medicinal plants are explored and their active phyto-constituents have been discovered, the synergistic role of plant products in disease amelioration has been established and the introduction of such alternative medicinal remedies in daily life has been increased.

Acmella uliginosa (Sw.) Cass. (Occasionally termed as AU in this paper) is an indigenous herb belonging to the Class Magnoliopsida, Order Asterales, Family Asteraceae. The plant is also known as Akarkara or Gorokhbon in Bengali. This Worldwide distributed plant is naturalized in India. It has conical small sized yellow flowers (Fig. 1) and the whole plant is claimed to possess medicinal properties (Sinha, 1996). The flower, commonly known as ‘toothache plant’, when chewed, has a pungent taste which is followed by tingle and numbness of the tongue and often used to cure mouth ulcer related pain (Ong *et al.*, 2011; Chakraborty *et al.*, 2004). This plant has a potent

Fig. 1: *Acmella uliginosa* plant with flower. In the upper left corner, inset shows the illustrated photograph of *Acmella uliginosa* flower.

antimicrobial activity and the antioxidant effect (Lagnika *et al.*, 2016). Recently the synergistic role of AU flower crude homogenate combined with crude Aloe gel has shown a potent anti-rheumatic activity (Paul *et al.*, 2016). This plant is very popular and used as folk medicine among the tribal communities and Rajbanshi people from North-East India. The *in vivo* anti-inflammatory property of this plant was further confirmed in this work by assessing the membrane stabilizing and protein anti-denaturing properties of the methanolic flower extract *in vitro*.

It is well established that the lysosomal contents are capable of inducing inflammation. During inflammation, while playing their defensive role, most immune cells release lysosomal content. The lysosomal enzymes act non-specifically on all adjacent cells and causes further tissue damage by rupturing their membrane. (Chayen and Bitensky, 1971). Lysosomal membrane has a membrane structure similar to that of the red blood cells. The erythrocyte membrane is thus considered as a model of the lysosomal membrane (Anosike *et al.*, 2012). It is expected that the plant extract capable of preventing the rupture of the erythrocyte membrane would also prevent the damage to the lysosomal membrane of the effected tissue during inflammation resulting in the inhibition of lysosomal content release. An increase in the denaturation of protein has been a key factor for the detection of inflammation (Mizushima, 1964). The inhibition of protein denaturation *in vitro* by the plant extract also adds a significant function of the plant extract in the protection of cell membrane stability and serum protein content in inflamed condition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of plant materials and authentication: Naturally grown wild *Acmella uliginosa* (Sw.) Cass. Plant flowers were collected by the authors from the North Bengal University campus area which is located in the sub-Himalayan Terai region

of West Bengal. All the plants were identified by Plant Taxonomy and Biosystematics laboratory in the Department of Botany, University of North Bengal and a voucher specimen (Accession-NBU09884) was submitted at the herbarium for future reference.

Preparation of plant materials and extraction procedure: The collected plant parts (flower) were separated from undesirable materials of plants and properly cleaned and washed with distilled water to remove the dust particles. The flowers were then dried in shade at room temperature for 2 weeks and then the dried flowers were grinded to fine powder using an electrical grinder. This fine powder was decanted with methanol and kept in a shaking incubator (Riviera, India) at room temperature for 48 hours. After that the supernatant liquid was collected and filtered through the Whatman No1 filter paper. The resultant *Acmella uliginosa* methanolic extract (AUME) was concentrated and condensed into a thick end product by inert nitrogen gas flow. Obtained extracts were stored at 4°C up to the commencement of experiments.

Drugs and Chemicals: Molecular biology grade monosodium di-hydrogen orthophosphate (NaH_2PO_4) and di-sodium hydrogen orthophosphate (Na_2HPO_4) was purchased from Thomas Baker, India; Sodium chloride (NaCl) was purchased from Merck, India; Diclofenac sodium was procured as Voveran-SR (Novartis India Ltd., Mumbai, India) and Indomethacin (Jagsonpal Pharmaceutical Ltd., New Delhi, India) was purchased from local drug suppliers and used as standard drug of inflammation. Biochemical assay kit for total protein was procured from Coral Clinical Systems, India.

Collection of blood samples: Fresh whole blood (3 ml) was collected intravenously from a healthy volunteer who did not take any NSAID at least 15 days prior to the experiment. The collected blood was kept in a test tube with an anti-coagulant ethylene-diamine-tetraacetic acid (EDTA) under

standard laboratory conditions.

Preparation of erythrocyte suspension: To prepare the erythrocyte suspension, 3ml of blood (containing anti-coagulant EDTA) was centrifuged (Sigma 3K30, Germany) at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes, and the supernatant was measured by pipetting. A volume of normal saline (0.9%) equivalent to that of the supernatant was used to dissolve the red blood pellets and washed it for 3 times. The volume of the dissolved red blood pellets was measured and reconstituted as a 40% (v/v) suspension with isotonic buffer solution (pH 7.4). Thus the reconstituted red blood cell (resuspended supernatant) was the stock erythrocyte (hRBC) suspension. The final count of RBC was 2.3×10^6 / ml. This was considered as the stock sample.

Membrane stabilizing activity:

Hypotonic solution-induced hemolysis

The effect of the AUME on hRBC hemolysis induced by hypotonic solution was assessed by a modified method of Shinde *et al.*, (1999). For the test, AUME was dissolved at a concentration of 100, 200 and 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ in 5 ml of hypotonic solution (distilled water) in one set of centrifuge tubes. In another set of centrifuge tubes, isotonic buffer solution (5 ml) containing similar graded doses of the AUME (100, 200 and 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) were taken. In standard group, Indomethacin (200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) was used as a standard drug. Control tubes contained only 5 ml of the distilled water as hypotonic solution and no AUME or standard drug was added. The experiments were carried out in triplicate pairs (per dose) of the centrifuge tubes. 100 μl of stock erythrocyte suspension was then added to each of the centrifuge tubes and after gentle mixing, the mixtures were incubated for 1 hour at 37°C temperature. After incubation, the mixture was centrifuged for 3 min at 1300 g in room temperature and the absorbance (OD) of the supernatant was measured at 540 nm using double beam UV- VIS spectrophotometer (Ray-Leigh UV-

2601, Beijing, China). The percentage hemolysis was calculated by assuming the hemolysis produced in the presence of distilled water (hypotonic solution) to be 100%. Thus the percent inhibition of haemolysis was calculated using the following equation.

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of haemolysis} = [1 - (\text{OD}_2 - \text{OD}_1) / (\text{OD}_3 - \text{OD}_1)] \times 100$$

Where,

OD_1 = Absorbance of test sample in isotonic solution

OD_2 = Absorbance of test sample in hypotonic solution

OD_3 = Absorbance of control sample in hypotonic solution

Heat induced hemolysis

This test was carried out with the standard protocol describes by Shinde *et al.* (1999) with minor modifications. For this test, one untreated group, three experimental AUME treated groups and one standard drug group were considered. Centrifuged tubes were arranged in triplicate sets (3 sets per dose). First set, designated as control tubes contained only 5 ml of the distilled water (vehicle). In the experimental groups, AUME were dissolved in 5ml of isotonic phosphate buffer solution (pH 7.4) at a concentration of 100, 200 and 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. The standard drug dose group contained 5ml isotonic buffer solution containing indomethacin at a concentration of 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. An amount of 100 μl of erythrocyte suspension was added to each tube and mixed gently. The tubes were incubated at 54 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 min in a regulated water bath. After incubation period, the reaction mixture was centrifuged at 1300 g for 3 min in room temperature and the absorbance (OD) of the supernatant was measured at 540 nm. The percent inhibition of hemolysis by the AUME was calculated using the following equation (Tatiya and Saluja, 2011):

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of haemolysis} = [(\text{OD}_2 - \text{OD}_1) / \text{OD}_2] \times 100$$

Where,

OD_1 = Absorbance of heated test sample

OD_2 = Absorbance of heated control sample

Protein denaturation test: The test was performed as described by the published protocols (Mizushima and Kobayashi, 1968; Gupta *et al.*, 2015) with minor modifications. Egg albumin was used as protein source and the protein concentration was measured by commercial Folin-Lowry method-based biochemical kit following the manufacturers' protocol. The experiment was carried out in triplicate pairs (per dose). The reaction mixture (5 ml) consisted of 0.2 ml of egg albumin (from fresh hen's egg), 2.8 ml of phosphate buffered saline (PBS, pH 6.4) and 2 ml of varying concentrations of AUME resulting in the final reaction concentrations of 100, 200, 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. 2ml of distilled water served as the control group instead of AUME. Diclofenac sodium (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) was used as a standard drug. The reaction mixture was incubated at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 minutes in incubator and then the mixture was heated at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 minutes in a regulated water bath. The resulting solution was cooled down to room temperature and the turbidity of the solution was measured spectrophotometrically at 660 nm. The percentage inhibition of protein denaturation was calculated using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of protein denaturation} = [(\text{OD}_2 - \text{OD}_1) / \text{OD}_2] \times 100$$

Where,

OD_1 = Absorbance of heated test sample

OD_2 = Absorbance of heated control sample

Statistical analysis: All statistical analyses were done using GraphPad prism ver 6.01. Data were reported as mean \pm S.E.M. (Standard Error Mean) and were analyzed with one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons test. The results were considered statistically significant at $P \leq 0.05$ compared to the control group (distilled water). The **** denotes significance value at $P < 0.0001$.

Table 1: Inhibition properties of plant extract in membrane stabilization and protein denaturation compared to their standard drug groups (Indomethacin as a membrane stabilization and diclofenac as an anti-protein denaturation agent).

Test samples	Concentration (µg/ml)	Mean% of inhibition±SEM		
		Hypotonicity induced	Heat induced	Albumin denaturation
AUME	100	17.45±1.56	13.62±0.88	14.31±1.72
	200	30.07±2.47	15.81±0.79	23.35±1.26
	400	39.37±3.63	25.22±0.98	26.52±2.39
Indomethacin	200	59.77±2.10	43.73±1.54	
Diclofenac	100			55.85±3.47

Fig. 2: Hypotonicity-induced hemolysis test of hRBC treated with *Acmella uliginosa* flower methanolic extract. All data represents % of inhibition ± SEM. Significance value at P <0.0001 is indicated as ****. Indomethacin is used as a standard drug; untreated group is considered to exert 100% hemolysis.

Fig. 3: Heat induced hemolysis test of hRBC treated with *Acmella uliginosa* flower methanolic extract. All data represents % of inhibition ± SEM. Significance value at P <0.0001 is indicated as ****. Indomethacin is used as a standard drug; untreated group is considered to exert 100% hemolysis.

RESULTS

Effect of AUME on hypotonicity induced hemolysis of HRBCs: The standard NSAID drug indomethacin showed the highest protection ($59.77 \pm 2.10\%$). The AUME protected the human erythrocytes against hypotonicity-induced haemolysis in a concentration dependent manner (Table 1). Within experimental groups, the protective effect was best seen in $400 \mu\text{g/ml}$ AUME dose group ($39.37 \pm 3.63\%$). Results showed that the AUME dose groups ($100 \mu\text{g/ml}$, $200 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and $400 \mu\text{g/ml}$) significantly inhibited the hRBC hemolysis in hypotonic conditions as shown in (Fig. 2).

Effect of AUME on heat induced hemolysis of HRBCs: All the doses of AUME ($100 \mu\text{g/ml}$, $200 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and $400 \mu\text{g/ml}$) showed a significant inhibition against heat induced hemolysis of hRBCs (Table 1). Within experimental groups, maximum inhibition of $25.22 \pm 0.98\%$ was observed at $400 \mu\text{g/ml}$ dose group and standard NSAID indomethacin showed the maximum inhibition $43.73 \pm 1.54\%$ at the concentration of $200 \mu\text{g/ml}$. Percentage of inhibition of hemolysis caused by AUME in all experimental groups was found to be dose dependent and statistically significant (Fig. 3).

Effect of AUME on protein denaturation test: The concentration of the hen egg albumin was 6.30 g/dl following the Folin-Lowry method. In the present study the AUME showed mean inhibition of protein denaturation of 26.52% , 23.35% and 14.31% for the doses of $400 \mu\text{g/ml}$, $200 \mu\text{g/ml}$ and $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively (Table 1). The ability of AUME to inhibit the heat induced protein denaturation was statistically significant when compared to control dose (dH_2O) group (Fig. 4). Diclofenac, the standard NSAID drug, at a concentration of $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$ showed the highest percentage (55.85%) of protection.

DISCUSSION

In the present study, the *in-vitro* anti-inflammatory role of AUME has been evaluated

Fig. 4: Upper panel: Denaturation inhibition test of Hens albumin (standard protein) treated with *Acmella uliginosa* flower methanolic extract. All data represents % of inhibition \pm SEM. Significance value at $P < 0.0001$ is indicated as ****, $P < 0.001$ is indicated as ***. Diclofenac used as a standard drug; untreated group is considered to exert 100% denaturation. **Lower panel:** The turbidity of treated, untreated and control samples following protein denaturation test prior to optical density measurement. Left most test tube shows reference frame as distilled water.

using human RBC membrane stabilization test and protein denaturation test. The results of the study show that the AUME possesses a significant protective property against the heat and hypotonicity induced haemolysis of the hRBCs membrane. AUME also decreases the protein denaturation significantly.

Erythrocyte membrane stability test has been a well documented study to screen the possible anti-inflammatory effect of synthetic drug as well as various traditional herbal plants extracts (Shinde *et al.*, 1999). Lysis of lysosomal vesicles and the release of lysosomal content is a key procedure of systemic inflammation elicited by immune cells. These lysosomal enzymes are capable of inducing the inflammatory processes (Anderson, 1970). Substances capable to stabilize the lysosomal membrane structure prevent the membrane rupture and contribute to the anti-inflammatory effects (Chayen and Bitensky, 1971). Thus a stabilized membrane prevents the progression of inflammation and lowers the oxidative damage caused by the free radical generation following inflammation. Traditional NSAID drugs reduce the consequences of inflammation by either stabilizing the membrane or by inhibiting the release of lysosomal contents (Anosike *et al.*, 2012). In fact, the role of NSAIDs in membrane stabilization was postulated before the discovery of their role in Cox pathway (Mizushima, 1964). The human erythrocyte membrane was considered as a model of lysosomal membrane. The exposure of erythrocyte membrane in hypotonic solution, heat and oxidizing agents causes the breakage of the membrane, oxidation of hemoglobin and hemolysis of the cells (Ferrali *et al.*, 1992). In the hypotonic solution, the hemolysis is caused by the excessive accumulation of fluid within the cell resulting in the rupturing of its membrane. When the body temperature is elevated, human erythrocytes is likely to rupture resulting in hemolysis (Aloni *et al.*, 1977). So, any expected membrane stabilizer drug should offer a significant protection over the hemolysis process of erythrocytes and deliver the anti-inflammatory property. In our study we have found a dose dependent relationship of AUME against both hypotonicity and heat induced hemolysis (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 respectively). The protective effect of AUME was best seen in hypotonicity-induced hemolysis followed by heat induced hemolysis (Table 1). Therefore, AUME may

inhibit the release of lysosomal content of neutrophil during the inflammatory processes. A possible explanation for the membrane stabilizing activity of AUME could be an increase in surface area/volume ratio of the cell which could be brought about by an expansion of membrane, shrinkage of cellular dimension by some means or (Abe *et al.*, 1991) by a stabilization of the skeletal proteins such as tropomyosin (Chasis and Mohandas, 1986; An *et al.*, 2007) (Fig. 4).

In the present study, the results of the protein denaturation test, the denaturation of egg albumin was induced by heat treatment. Most biological proteins lose their integrity and biological function when denatured. The functional three-dimensional structure is broken or changed following the heat exposure. Denaturation of proteins is a well-documented feature in chronic inflammatory diseases like rheumatoid arthritis (Rowley *et al.*, 1986; Ukaji *et al.*, 1999). Furthermore, denatured proteins had the capacity to induce delayed type II hypersensitivity (Gell and Benacerraf, 1959). However, conventional NSAID drugs can inhibit the heat induced protein denaturation (Grant *et al.*, 1970; Mizushima and Kobayashi, 1968). The role of AU flower homogenate was already known to be a potent anti-arthritis agent (Paul *et al.*, 2016), the analgesic property of the plant is also well established. The present study added a new dimension to the existing information regarding the anti-inflammatory roles of the plant in *in vitro* condition.

CONCLUSION

The analyses of the result and detailed logical interpretation establish AUME as a potent anti-inflammatory agent in both *in vivo* and *in vitro* conditions. The possible involvement of the extract in the integration of cellular structure through molecular interactions can be better studied in experimental and *in silico* conditions. Furthermore, exploration of the principle phyto-constituents can be achieved through sophisticated separation

techniques. All these information may establish the underlying effective pathway of inflammation inhibition by AUME.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Declared none by the authors.

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